

BIG DATA ANALYTICS**Mehdizade M.***Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University (ASOIU)***ABSTRACT**

In the information era, enormous amounts of data have become available on hand to decision makers. Big data refers to datasets that are not only big, but also high in variety and velocity, which makes them difficult to handle using traditional tools and techniques. Due to the rapid growth of such data, solutions need to be studied and provided in order to handle and extract value and knowledge from these datasets. Furthermore, decision makers need to be able to gain valuable insights from such varied and rapidly changing data, ranging from daily transactions to customer interactions and social network data. Such value can be provided using big data analytics, which is the application of advanced analytics techniques on big data. This paper aims to analyze some of the different analytics methods and tools which can be applied to big data, as well as the opportunities provided by the application of big data analytics in various decision domains.

Keywords: Big Data, Data mining, Analytics, Decision making.

Introduction

Consider a scenario devoid of data storage: where every piece of information, transaction, or documented detail about individuals or organizations disappears once it's used. In such a world, organizations would lack the capacity to extract valuable insights, conduct in-depth analyses, and leverage new opportunities and advantages. This would encompass everything from customer details and product information to transaction records and employee data.

Data is the foundation upon which any organization thrives. Consider the vast amount of details and the surge of data now available due to technological advancements and the internet. With improved storage capabilities and data collection methods, enormous amounts of data have become readily accessible. Every second, more data is generated and needs to be stored and analyzed to extract value.

Furthermore, data has become cheaper to store, so organizations need to get as much value as possible from the huge amounts of stored data. The size, diversity, and rapid evolution of such data demand new types of big data analytics and different storage and analysis methods. These vast amounts of big data need thorough analysis to extract relevant information. Accordingly, some of the various big data tools, methods, and technologies which can be applied are discussed, and their applications and opportunities provided in several decision domains are portrayed.

Additionally, our collection predominantly comprises research from leading journals, conferences, and white papers by major industry corporations. Most papers exploring big data analytics, its tools, methods, and applications were identified as conference papers and white papers. Although academia contributes to the research on big data analytics, many advancements and new technologies from industry are primarily discussed in industry papers.

Big Data Analytics

The term "Big Data" has been employed to refer to datasets that have expanded to a scale where they pose challenges for traditional database systems to effectively manage. They are data sets whose size is beyond the ability of commonly used software tools and storage systems to capture, store, manage, as well as process the data within a tolerable elapsed time.

Big data sizes are continually increasing, currently ranging from a few dozen terabytes (TB) to multiple petabytes (PB) within a single dataset. Consequently, challenges associated with big data include capturing, storing, searching, sharing, analyzing, and visualizing data. Today, enterprises are examining large volumes of highly detailed data to uncover previously unknown insights. Big data analytics involves applying advanced analytical techniques to these extensive datasets. Analytics based on large data samples can reveal and drive business changes. However, managing larger datasets is becoming increasingly difficult.

In this section, we will begin by discussing the characteristics and importance of big data. Analyzing larger and more complex datasets often yields business benefits, especially when real-time or near-real-time capabilities are required; this, however, necessitates new data architectures, analytical methods, and tools. Therefore, the following section will detail the tools and methods for big data analytics, starting with storage and management, then moving on to analytic processing. It will conclude with an overview of various big data analyses that have gained prominence.

2.1 Characteristics of Big Data

Big data is characterized by its scale, distribution, diversity, and timeliness, necessitating new technical architectures, analytics, and tools to derive insights that unlock new business value. Three main features define big data: volume, variety, and velocity, often referred to as the three V's. Volume denotes the size of the data, velocity refers to the speed at which data changes or is generated, and variety encompasses the different formats, types, and uses of data, along with the various methods of analysis.

Data volume is the primary attribute of big data, measured in terabytes (TB) or petabytes (PB), and can also be quantified by the number of records, transactions, tables, or files. Big data is growing larger partly due to the increased variety of data sources, including logs, clickstreams, and social media. Analytics now incorporate not only structured data but also unstructured data, such as text and human language, and semi-structured data like XML or RSS feeds. Additionally, data from audio, video, and other devices, which is hard to categorize, contributes to big data. Multi-dimensional data from data warehouses can also provide historical

context, making variety as significant as volume in big data.

Furthermore, big data is characterized by its velocity or speed, which refers to how frequently data is generated or delivered. The forefront of big data includes streaming data, collected in real-time from websites. Some researchers and organizations have introduced a fourth V, veracity, which focuses on data quality. Veracity assesses the quality of big data, considering factors like inconsistency, incompleteness, ambiguity, latency, deception, and approximations.

2.2 Big Data Analytics Tools and Methods

As technology evolves and organizations deal with increasing volumes of data flowing in and out daily, there arises a demand for faster and more efficient methods of data flowing in and out of organizations daily, there has become a need for faster and more efficient ways of analyzing such data. Having piles of data on hand is no longer enough to make efficient decisions at the right time.

Traditional data management and analysis techniques and infrastructures are no longer sufficient for analyzing such large datasets. Given that traditional data management and analysis techniques and infrastructures are no longer sufficient for analyzing such large datasets, there's a pressing need for new tools and methods specialized for big data analytics, along with the requisite architectures for storing and managing such data. Consequently, the emergence of big data has profound implications across various stages, from data collection to processing to final decision-making.

To address these challenges, we propose the Big Data, Analytics, and Decisions (B-DAD) framework, which integrates big data analytics tools and methods into the decision-making process. This framework aligns different big data storage, management, and processing tools, analytics methods, and visualization and evaluation tools with the various phases of decision-making.

The changes associated with big data analytics are evident in three main areas: big data storage and architecture, data and analytics processing, and the application of big data analyses for knowledge discovery and informed decision-making. While each area will be discussed further in this section, it's worth noting that big data remains an evolving field of research, with new findings and tools continuously developing, so this discussion may not cover all aspects comprehensively.

Big Data Storage and Management

When organizations grapple with big data, one of their primary challenges is determining where and how to store this data once it's acquired. Traditional methods of structured data storage and retrieval involve relational databases, data marts, and data warehouses. Data is uploaded to storage from operational data stores using Extract, Transform, Load (ETL) or Extract, Load, Transform (ELT) tools, which extract data from external sources, transform it to fit operational needs, and load it into the database or data warehouse. This process ensures that the data is cleaned, transformed, and cataloged before being made available for data mining and online analytical functions.

However, the big data environment necessitates a different approach, characterized by Magnetic, Agile, Deep (MAD) analysis skills, distinct from those of a traditional Enterprise Data Warehouse (EDW) environment. Traditional EDW approaches typically discourage the inclusion of new data sources until they are cleansed and integrated. In contrast, big data environments must be magnetic, attracting all data sources regardless of data quality due to the ubiquity of data today. Additionally, with the increasing number of data sources and the sophistication of data analyses, big data storage should enable analysts to rapidly produce and adapt data, requiring an agile database capable of synchronizing logical and physical contents with rapid data evolution. Finally, given the use of complex statistical methods in current data analyses and the need for analysts to study enormous datasets by drilling up and down, a big data repository must be deep and serve as a sophisticated algorithmic runtime engine.

Various solutions, including distributed systems and Massive Parallel Processing (MPP) databases, have been employed for big data to provide high query performance and platform scalability. Non-relational databases like Not Only SQL (NoSQL) were developed for storing and managing unstructured or non-relational data, aiming for massive scaling, data model flexibility, and simplified application development and deployment. Unlike relational databases, NoSQL databases separate data management and data storage, focusing on high-performance scalable data storage while allowing data management tasks to be written in the application layer instead of database-specific languages.

In-memory databases manage data in server memory, eliminating disk input/output (I/O) and enabling real-time responses from the database. Storing the primary database in silicon-based main memory results in significant performance improvements, enabling the development of entirely new applications. In-memory databases are increasingly used for advanced analytics on big data, particularly to accelerate access to and scoring of analytic models for analysis, providing scalability for big data and speed for discovery analytics.

Alternatively, Hadoop is a framework for performing big data analytics, offering reliability, scalability, and manageability by implementing the MapReduce paradigm, as discussed in the following section, and integrating storage and analytics. Hadoop consists of two main components: Hadoop Distributed File System (HDFS) for big data storage and MapReduce for big data analytics. HDFS provides a redundant and reliable distributed file system optimized for large files, where a single file is split into blocks and distributed across cluster nodes. Data is stored in replicated file blocks across multiple Data Nodes, with the Name Node serving as a regulator between the client and the Data Node, directing the client to the specific Data Node containing the requested data.

Big Data Analytic Processing

After big data storage, the next critical aspect is analytic processing, which involves four essential requirements. First, fast data loading is necessary to minimize interference with query executions caused by

disk and network traffic during data loading. Second, fast query processing is vital to meet the demands of heavy workloads and real-time requests, ensuring high query processing speeds even as the number of queries rapidly increases. Third, highly efficient utilization of storage space is crucial due to the rapid growth in user activities and the demand for scalable storage capacity and computing power. Limited disk space requires effective management of data storage during processing to maximize space utilization. Finally, strong adaptivity to highly dynamic workload patterns is essential as big data sets are analyzed by different applications and users for various purposes and in different ways.

MapReduce, a parallel programming model inspired by functional languages, is well-suited for big data processing and serves as the core of Hadoop for data processing and analytics functions. The MapReduce paradigm focuses on scaling out by adding more computers or resources, rather than scaling up by increasing the power or storage capacity of a single computer. This paradigm breaks tasks down into stages and executes them in parallel to reduce the time needed to complete the task.

In a MapReduce job, the first phase involves mapping input values to a set of key/value pairs as output. The "Map" function partitions large computational tasks into smaller tasks and assigns them to appropriate key/value pairs. For example, unstructured data like text can be mapped to a structured key/value pair, where the key could represent a word and the value could indicate the number of occurrences of that word. The output of the mapping phase serves as input to the "Reduce" function, which collects and combines this output by aggregating values sharing the same key value to produce the result of the computational task.

MapReduce relies on two main nodes: the Job Tracker and the Task Tracker nodes. The Job Tracker is responsible for distributing the mapper and reducer functions to available Task Trackers, as well as monitoring the results. It assigns portions of input files on the Hadoop Distributed File System (HDFS) to map tasks running on nodes. Task Tracker nodes execute the jobs and communicate results back to the Job Tracker, often through files and directories in HDFS to minimize inter-node communication.

3. Big Data Analytics and Decision Making

From the perspective of decision-makers, the significance of big data lies in its ability to provide valuable information and knowledge upon which to base decisions. The managerial decision-making process has been a well-covered topic in research over the years.

Big data is increasingly becoming a crucial asset for decision-makers. The availability of large volumes of highly detailed data from various sources such as scanners, mobile phones, loyalty cards, the web, and social media platforms presents significant opportunities for organizations. However, these benefits can only be realized if the data is properly analyzed to reveal valuable insights, enabling decision-makers to capitalize on opportunities arising from historic and real-time data generated through supply chains, production processes, customer behaviors, and more.

Organizations are traditionally accustomed to analyzing internal data like sales, shipments, and inventory. However, there is now a need to analyze external data such as customer markets and supply chains, and big data can provide cumulative value and knowledge in this regard. With the increasing sizes and types of unstructured data available, making more informed decisions based on meaningful inferences drawn from the data becomes imperative.

In response to this need, the B-DAD framework was developed to map big data tools and techniques into the decision-making process, with the aim of enhancing the quality of decision-making concerning big data. The framework encompasses several phases:

1. **Intelligence Phase:** Data is collected from internal and external sources to identify problems and opportunities. Big data sources are identified, and data is gathered, processed, stored, and migrated to end-users.

2. **Design Phase:** Possible courses of action are developed and analyzed through model planning, data analytics, and analysis.

3. **Choice Phase:** Methods are used to evaluate the impacts of proposed solutions or courses of action from the design phase.

4. **Implementation Phase:** The proposed solution from the previous phase is implemented.

As the volume of big data continues to grow exponentially, organizations across different sectors are increasingly interested in how to manage and analyze such data. They are rushing to seize the opportunities offered by big data, adopting big data analytics to unlock economic value and make better and faster decisions. This section focuses on various proposed and implemented applications of big data analytics and how they can aid organizations in gaining valuable insights and enhancing decision-making.

According to research by Manyika et al., big data can enable companies to create new products and services, enhance existing ones, and invent entirely new business models. Applications of big data analytics in areas such as customer intelligence, supply chain intelligence, performance, quality and risk management, and fraud detection can benefit industries such as manufacturing, retail, central government, healthcare, telecom, and banking, as highlighted by Cebr's study.

3.1 Customer Intelligence

Big data analytics indeed has significant potential for enhancing customer intelligence, and its applications can yield substantial benefits for industries like retail, banking, and telecommunications. Big data can create transparency and make relevant data more easily accessible to stakeholders in a timely manner. Big data analytics can provide organizations with the ability to profile and segment customers based on different socio-economic characteristics, as well as increase levels of customer satisfaction and retention. This can allow them to make more informed marketing decisions, and market to different segments based on their preferences along with the recognition of sales and marketing opportunities. Moreover, social media can be used to inform companies what their customers like. By performing sentiment analysis on this data, firms can be alerted beforehand when customers are turning against them or

shifting to different products, and accordingly take action.

Additionally, using SNAs to monitor customer sentiments towards brands, and identify influential individuals, can help organizations react to trends and perform direct marketing. Big data analytics can also enable the construction of predictive models for customer behavior and purchase patterns, therefore raising overall profitability. Even organizations which have used segmentation for many years are beginning to deploy more sophisticated big data techniques, such as real-time micro segmentation of customers, in order to target promotions and advertising. Consequently, big data analytics can benefit organizations by enabling better targeted social influencer marketing, defining and predicting trends from market sentiments, as well as analyzing and understanding churn and other customer behaviors.

3.2 Supply Chain and Performance Management

Big data analytics offers significant advantages in supply chain management by enabling organizations to forecast demand changes and align their supply accordingly. This capability can greatly benefit industries such as manufacturing, retail, transportation, and logistics.

By analyzing data on stock utilization and geospatial information on deliveries, organizations can automate replenishment decisions, reducing lead times and minimizing costs, delays, and process interruptions. Additionally, big data analytics enables organizations to make informed decisions about changing suppliers based on factors like quality or price competitiveness, by monitoring supplier performance data. Moreover, organizations can quickly run alternate pricing scenarios to optimize inventories and increase profit margins.

Furthermore, big data analytics facilitates the identification of root causes of costs and enhances planning and forecasting processes in supply chain management. By analyzing large datasets, organizations can gain insights into inefficiencies and areas for improvement, leading to better resource allocation and decision-making.

In addition to supply chain management, big data analytics can also bring significant benefits to performance management, particularly in industries such as government and healthcare. Predictive analytics tools can help monitor and forecast staff performance, allowing departments to align strategic objectives with service or user outcomes, thereby increasing efficiencies.

Moreover, the availability and accessibility of big data and performance information enable the implementation of predictive key performance indicators (KPIs), balanced scorecards, and dashboards within organizations. This introduces operational benefits by enabling the monitoring of performance, improving transparency, setting objectives, and enhancing planning and management functions.

Overall, big data analytics offers valuable opportunities for organizations to optimize their supply chain management processes, improve performance management, and drive efficiencies across various industries.

3.3 Quality Management and Improvement

Big data holds immense potential for quality management across industries like manufacturing, energy and utilities, telecommunications, and healthcare. By leveraging big data analytics, organizations can enhance profitability, reduce costs, and improve the quality of goods and services provided.

In manufacturing, predictive analytics on big data can minimize performance variability and prevent quality issues by providing early warning alerts. This can lead to reductions in scrap rates, decreased time to market, and improvements in manufacturing lead times. Real-time data analysis and monitoring of machine logs enable swift decision-making for quality management, contributing to overall process optimization.

Similarly, in the energy and utilities sector, big data analytics can optimize network demand monitoring and bandwidth forecasting in response to customer behavior. This enables utilities to better manage resources, enhance service reliability, and improve customer satisfaction.

In telecommunications, big data analytics facilitates real-time monitoring of network demand and forecasting of bandwidth requirements, enabling operators to optimize network performance and deliver superior service quality to customers.

Moreover, healthcare IT systems can benefit from big data analytics by communicating and integrating patient data across different departments and institutions while maintaining privacy controls. Analysis of electronic health records improves continuity of care and enables prediction and comparison of treatments and outcomes. Additionally, continuous monitoring of patients using sensors in hospitals and homes allows for real-time analysis of patient data, facilitating early detection of health anomalies and improving adherence to prescriptions.

In transportation, big data analytics transforms traffic management by predicting and preventing traffic jams, enhancing safety, and optimizing traffic flow. Intelligent connected cars enable smart routing based on real-time traffic information, automatic calls for help in case of emergencies, and timely alerts about accidents and congested areas.

Furthermore, big data analytics contributes to better understanding of weather and climate changes, benefiting industries reliant on weather forecasts such as agriculture, tourism, and transportation. With advanced sensors and analysis techniques, organizations can predict weather-related natural disasters and take preventive or adaptive measures in advance.

Overall, big data analytics offers extensive opportunities for improving quality management, enhancing operational efficiency, and driving innovation across various sectors, ultimately leading to better outcomes for businesses, citizens, and society as a whole.

3.4 Risk Management and Fraud Detection

Big data analytics offers significant advantages in risk management for industries such as investment banking, retail banking, insurance, and government. Given the critical role of risk evaluation in the financial services sector, big data analytics can aid in investment selection by analyzing the probability of gains versus

losses. It allows for the comprehensive analysis of both internal and external data to assess risk exposures dynamically.

One of the key benefits of big data analytics in risk management is its ability to quantify risks effectively. High-performance analytics can integrate risk profiles from various departments into enterprise-wide risk profiles, providing decision-makers with a holistic view of different risk types and their interrelationships. This facilitates better risk mitigation strategies and enhances overall risk management practices.

Moreover, big data tools and technologies enable organizations to manage the exponential growth of network-generated data and address database performance issues. By enhancing cyber analytics and data-intensive computing solutions, organizations can leverage multiple data streams and automated analyses to defend against cyber and network attacks effectively.

Big data analytics also plays a crucial role in fraud detection, particularly in government, banking, and insurance sectors. By leveraging big data analytics, organizations can detect and prevent fraudulent activities more efficiently. They can match electronic data across various sources, public and private, and conduct faster analytics to identify suspicious patterns.

Customer intelligence is another area where big data analytics contributes to fraud detection. By modeling normal customer behavior and flagging outlier occurrences, organizations can detect suspicious activities accurately. Additionally, big data analytics enables systems to learn new fraud patterns and adapt accordingly, staying ahead of fraudsters who evolve to evade detection.

Social network analyses (SNAs) can further enhance fraud detection efforts by identifying networks of collaborating fraudsters and uncovering evidence of fraudulent claims. By leveraging big data tools, techniques, and governance processes, organizations can significantly increase the speed and accuracy of identifying and detecting fraudulent transactions across all available datasets, leading to more effective prevention and recovery of fraudulent activities.

Conclusion

In this study, we delved into the burgeoning field of big data, which has garnered considerable attention owing to its perceived vast opportunities and advantages. In our current information-driven era, an abundance of diverse, rapidly generated data contains intricate details and patterns that hold invaluable knowledge waiting to be extracted and harnessed. Therefore, employing big data analytics can facilitate transformative changes in business and improve decision-making processes by applying advanced analytical techniques to uncover hidden insights and valuable information.

We conducted a comprehensive literature review to analyze the concepts of big data analytics and its significance in decision-making processes. This involved

examining the nature and importance of big data, as well as exploring various tools and methods employed in big data storage, management, and analytics processing. Additionally, we explored advanced data analytics techniques that can be applied to big data to extract meaningful information.

By leveraging big data analytics, organizations can extract valuable insights to inform decision-making processes and drive informed decisions. We identified numerous areas where big data analytics can contribute to decision-making across various sectors, including customer intelligence, fraud detection, and supply chain management. Furthermore, we highlighted the broad applicability of big data analytics across industries such as healthcare, retail, telecom, and manufacturing.

Our research provided examples of various big data tools, methods, and technologies that can be utilized, offering users insights into necessary technologies and developers ideas for enhancing big data analytics solutions to support decision-making processes. Ultimately, we underscored the importance of big data analytics in navigating the challenges posed by the vast volumes, velocities, and varieties of data sources, while also recognizing the need for future research to focus on developing frameworks or roadmaps for effective big data management.

We firmly believe that big data analytics holds significant promise in our data-driven age, offering unprecedented insights and benefits to decision-makers across various domains. With proper utilization and application, big data analytics has the potential to drive advancements across scientific, technological, and humanitarian realms, paving the way for transformative progress.

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